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FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF DISPERSIBLE PELLETS OF *LAGENARIA SICERARIA* BY BOX BEHNKHEN DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

In the current dispersible pellets were prepared and further evaluated. The pellets were prepared by extrusion spheronization technique, by Box–Behnken experimental design to set up the relation between independent variables, citric acid (X_1), Ludiflash (X_2) and sodium bicarbonate (X_3), and dependent variable and to acquire optimal formula of process using Response Surface Methodology (RSM). Optimization studies were utilized to study the effect of different variables on the formulated pellets. To estimate the significance of the model ANOVA test was performed. A model is considered significant, if the p - value is less than 0.05. From the study; it was found that F16 was the optimized formulation, with DT of 40 secs, with good particle size and other evaluation parameters.. The values of estimation error proved validity of the used arithmetical method. The surface morphology of the pellets was studied by use of optical microscope. Thus formulated pellets offered narrow particle size distribution, good flow property, angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density and decrease in moisture. Conclusion: The use of proper selection of superdisintegrant and its concentration showed good disintegration time of less than 60 seconds. By use of optimization study, pellets were successfully prepared.

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INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, the use of herbal medicines has widely increased. And market for herbal medicine is expected to grow extensively in coming future. These herbal medicines can be formulated in various dosage forms as granules, pellets, tablets, capsules etc. From these, the pellets offer number of advantages over different dosage forms. Preparation of pellets by extrusion spheronization techniques is widely used. *Lagenaria siceraria* [LS] is one of the well-accepted vegetable that is cultivated in warmer parts of India [1]. A number of drugs and herbals can be included to form dispersible pellets that provide advantages of good patient compliance [2-5]. So use of this vegetable juice and this technique of extrusion spheronization are utilized in formulating dispersible pellets. As juice of this vegetable has stability problems, so an attempt was made to prepare dispersible pellets of it, to overcome the problem. For formulation of dispersible pellets, proper selection of excipients is rudimental, so they disintegrate immediately within 15 to 60 secs, in the oral cavity. Thus, the aim of this study was to use optimization studies for development of dispersible pellets of *Lagenaria siceraria*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The plant material was purchased from local market. Avicel PH 101 was purchased Company. PVP K-25 was purchased from Himedia Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, Maharashtra, India.

Plant collection:

Lagenaria siceraria [LS] was collected from local market and it was authenticated from Botanical survey of India (BSI), the number being BSI/WRC/Tech/2014 dated 20/11/2014

Preparation of dispersible pellets by extrusion–spheronization

The dispersible pellets were prepared by use of juice of *Lagenaria siceraria*, Avicel PH 101, citric acid, PVP K-25, PEG 8000 superdisintegrant-Ludiflash and sodium bicarbonate, by BoxBehnken design [6]. The parameters for extrusion spheronization were considered to get optimized formulation. The powder excipients were sieved by 40 mesh sieve and mixed for 5 min. The bottle guard juice was mixed to the above excipients, to form wet mass, ready for extrusion. Further the wet mass was extruded through extruder (VJ instrument, India) that was equipped with 0.8mm screen, and it was maintained at 50 rpm. The extrudates were then collected on butter paper and added to spheronizer at 1200 rpm for 3 min (VJ instrument, India) that was fitted with a cross hatched plate with the length of each groove of 2 mm. The pellets were collected through spheronizer, and dried in dessicator.

Design of experiments: Box Behnken design was used for the study. A 3-factor, 3-level design was used for exploring the effect of the factors on the response by use of Design Expert version 11.0.

Table 1: Independent Variables in Design.

Variables	-1	0	+1
Citric acid (X ₁)	5	8.5	12
Ludiflash (X ₂)	10	15	20
Sodium bicarbonate(X ₃)	5	10	15

Table 2: Composition of dispersible pellets by Box Behnken design.

Runs	Factor 1 A: Citric acid (g)	Factor 2 B: Ludiflash (g)	Factor 3 C : Sodium bicarbonate (g)
1	12	10	10
2	5	15	15
3	5	20	10
4	8.5	15	10
5	5	10	10
6	8.5	20	5
7	8.5	10	5
8	12	15	15
9	8.5	10	15
10	8.5	15	10
11	8.5	15	10
12	12	20	10
13	5	15	5
14	8.5	15	10
15	8.5	15	10
16	8.5	20	15
17	12	15	5

Evaluation of formulated dispersible pellets

To verify the characteristics of the formulated pellets, they were evaluated for different tests, as mentioned below

Friability test

This was done by use of Roche friabilator (LabIndia, Mumbai, India). A preweighed sample was placed in the friabilator along with 25 steel balls, each 2 mm in diameter. After 100 revolutions at 25 rpm, the mass retained on 25 mesh sieve was weighed, and friability was calculated as the percentage loss of mass between the initial and final weights of sample.

Flow properties

Flow properties were evaluated in terms of angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density and Hausner's ratio.

Angle of Repose

It was determined by use of fixed funnel method. Funnel was secured with its tip at a given height (h), above a graph paper that is placed on a flat horizontal surface. The pellets were poured through the funnel until the top of the conical pile just touches the tip of the funnel. The radius of the base of the conical pile was measured. The angle of repose (θ) was calculated using the following

$$\text{formula: } \tan \theta = h/r$$

Where, θ = Angle of repose, h = Height of the cone, r = Radius of the cone base.

Bulk Density

Pellets were introduced into a dry 100 ml cylinder, without compacting. The pellets were carefully leveled without compacting and the unsettled apparent volume, V_o , was noted. The bulk density was calculated using the following:

$$\text{formula. } \rho_b = M / V_o$$

Where, ρ_b = Apparent bulk density, M = Weight of sample, V = Apparent volume of powder

Tapped Density

Once the bulk density is known, the cylinder containing the pellets was tapped 500 times initially followed by an additional taps of 750 times until difference between succeeding measurement is less than 2% and then tapped volume, V_f was measured, to the nearest graduated unit. The tapped density was calculated, in gm per ml, using the following

$$\text{formula. } \rho_{tap} = M / V_f$$

Where, ρ_{tap} = Tapped density, M = Weight of sample, V_f = Tapped volume of powder.

Hausner's Ratio

Hausner's ratio is one of the indirect guide for ease of powder flow. The formula, for it is Hausner's Ratio = Tapped density (ρ_t) / Bulk density (ρ_b) Where, ρ_t tapped density and ρ_b is bulk density. Lower Hausner's ratio.

Shape Analysis

The pellets were analyzed for shape analysis by use of optical microscope. At least 20 pellets from each batch were randomly selected. The pellets were mounted on a surface of optical microscope, and the images of the pellets were captured.

Pellet Disintegration Test

The pellet disintegration in water was evaluated by a tablet disintegration test apparatus. 100 mg pellets were placed along with a plastic disc in each tube and they were inserted in the disintegration test apparatus maintained at $37^\circ\text{C} \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. Disintegration test was carried out three times for each formulation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For extrusion–spheronization, MCC is found to be the ideal, as it possesses the appropriate properties, necessary for this technique, with necessary rheological properties. MCC is standard, due to its absorptive property to retain water in large quantity, due to its large surface area and internal porosity that is necessary to facilitate extrusion and enhance plasticity of the mass, for further spheronization. Pellets with MCC by extrusion–spheronization were spherical in nature and had low friability. Eight formulations of dispersible pellets were prepared using extrusion–spheronization technique.

The evaluation properties of dispersible pellets like friability test, flow properties, bulk density, tapped density, Hausner's ratio of all batches indicating good to fair flow ability as shown in Table 3. The pellets were found to be spherical in nature, under optical microscope.

Table 3: Flow property evaluation parameters for formulations.

Formulations	Bulk density	Tapped density	Hausner ratio	Angle of repose (°)	Friability (%)
F1	0.324±0.16	0.368±0.20	1.13	25.7±0.18	0.05
F2	0.345±0.12	0.378±0.31	1.09	25.4±0.23	0.04
F3	0.328±0.15	0.385±0.23	1.17	29.7±0.15	0.07
F4	0.318±0.20	0.374±0.21	1.17	30.5±0.17	0.02
F5	0.314±0.17	0.350±0.23	1.11	25.4±0.14	0.06
F6	0.320±0.18	0.340±0.35	1.06	31.6±0.20	0.02
F7	0.312±0.14	0.330±0.36	1.05	25.7±0.58	0.02
F8	0.324±0.15	0.342±0.21	1.05	30.5±0.50	0.01
F9	0.325±0.16	0.351±0.32	1.08	32.4±0.23	0.19
F10	0.318±0.20	0.374±0.21	1.17	30.5±0.17	0.02
F11	0.318±0.20	0.374±0.21	1.17	30.5±0.17	0.02
F12	0.340±0.17	0.365±0.24	1.07	30.9±0.17	0.20
F13	0.328±0.15	0.372±0.36	1.13	29.7±0.40	0.14
F14	0.318±0.20	0.374±0.21	1.17	30.5±0.17	0.02
F15	0.318±0.20	0.374±0.21	1.17	30.5±0.17	0.02
F16	0.332±0.12	0.354±0.21	1.06	29.7±0.42	0.07
F17	0.316±0.10	0.332±0.40	1.05	29.4±0.51	0.06

Optimization of results by response surface methodology analysis

From the response surface graph, it can be seen that, as the concentration of superdisintegrant increased, the disintegration time reduced. But after certain level of the superdisintegrant, the result was opposite, that is even on increasing the concentration of superdisintegrant, the disintegration time did not decrease, but increased. The range of Y1 was between 40 to 99 seconds respectively. The formulations formulated fitted to quadratic for Y1 using design expert software version 11.0. Values for R² is given in table 4.

Table 4: Summary of quadratic model for regression analysis of responses Y1 (DT).

Response	Model	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Predicted R
DT (secs)	Quadratic	0.8821	0.7306	0.440

Response surface analysis

For the response shown in Fig1 response surface graph was prepared. This plot is used to evaluate the interaction of the effects of both independent factor on one dependent response.

Fig 1 : Response surface plot for DT.

The Model F-value of 5.82 implies the model is significant $p < 0.0001$. The "Lack of Fit F-value" of 3.76 implies the Lack of Fit is not significant and it may be due to pure error. There is an 11.65% chance that a "Lack of Fit F-value" this large could occur due to noise. Values of $\text{Prob} > F < 0.0500$ show model terms are significant. From the response surface plot, it can be seen that as the concentration of superdisintegrant Ludiflash increase, the DT also increased [7-8].

Optimization model validation

In design expert software, ANOVA was used to generate statistical validity. Optimum formulations were given and based on the desirability the optimum result was selected. Design Expert software generated the contour plots. As the polynomial equation is generated in the software based on Y1 response the independent variables like X1, X2, X3 for the formulation was optimized.

CONCLUSION

Thus from the study, the optimum formula for formulation of dispersible pellets can be derived from Box Behnkhen design, with a disintegration time of 40seconds. The independent variables such as were chosen on the basis of preliminary trials which were carried before executing Design expert 11.0. Effect of independent variables on the dependent factors called response factors Y1 (DT) was evaluated. Formulated dispersible pellets were also evaluated for different parameters like flow properties and friability and the results shown were found to be satisfactory. Optimized formula was F16 that showed best results amongst all batches. The study suggested that formulation of dispersible pellets of *Lagenaria sciceria* were successfully carried.

ABBREVIATIONS:

RSM	- Response surface methodology
ANOVA	- Analysis of Variance
LS	- <i>Lagenaria siceraria</i>
PVP K-25	- Polyvinyl pyrrolidone
MCC	- Microcrystalline cellulose
DT	- Disintegration time

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

We declare that we have no conflict of interest

REFERENCES

1. Renner S, Pandey A. The Cucurbitaceae of India: Accepted names, synonyms, geographic distribution, and information on images and DNA sequences, 2013, PhytoKeys, (20): 53–118.
2. Mascia S, Seiler C, Fitzpatrick S, Wilsona DI. Extrusion-spheronization of microcrystalline cellulose pastes using anon-aqueous liquid binder. Int J Pharm, 2010, 389:1–9.
3. Gandhi R, Kaul CL, Panchagnula R. Extrusion and spheronization in the development of oral controlled-release dosage forms. Pharm Sci Technol Today, 1999, 2:160–70.
4. Gruber P. Easy to swallow oral medicament composition, 2004, US Patent No. 6,709,678.
5. Augello M, Vladyka RS, Dell SM. Taste masked pharmaceutical compositions, 1999, US Patent No. 5,904,937.
6. Box G, Behnken D. Some new three level designs for the study of quantitative variables. Technometrics, 1960, 2(4):455-475.
7. Lakshmi P, Narendra Y. Comparative Evaluation of Natural And Synthetic Superdisintegrants In The Formulation of Fas Dissolving Tablets. Turk J Pharm Sci, 2013, 10(3), 35-366.
8. Sowmya C, Subba Reddy P, Rajeswary B, Reddy S. Preparation and Evaluation of Fast Disintegrating Tablets of Lamivudine Using Co-processed Excipients. Inventi Rapid: Novel Excipients, 2016, 1.8.

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